

Complete Solution to the Hubble tension from Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation Temperature

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Abstract:

This paper presents a complete solution to the current issue of Hubble tension that arises between Planck 2018 team and SHOES team. Herein we introduce a new constant named as "Dark Constant." Dark Constant is the ratio of X-Energy with the energy of Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation. While estimating X-Energy, we also show the relationship between X-Energy and Hubble's constant (H_0). In the same way we show relationship between Hubble's constant (H_0) and Cosmic Microwave Background Temperature (T). There by we derive a solution to the Hubble tension/issue, estimate the value for Dark Constant, and an estimate for the total age of the universe. This paper estimates the Temperature (T) when age of the universe was 1 second. The main finding of this paper is that the Hubble's constant (H_0) is proportional to the Cosmic Microwave Background temperature and according to this research the correct value for H_0 at 2.725K is 72.4646989313493 Km/s/Mpc. Thereby this research resolves the tension arising due to the differing values for H_0 presented by the various team.

Keywords:

Hubble constant, Hubble tension, CMB, CMB-Temperature, age of the universe, intergalactic, Dark Constant, Cosmic ladder.

1. Introduction:

In 1908, H.S Leavitt's discovery gave the relationship between period and Luminosity which was used to calculate the Cosmic distances from the earth to stars depending upon their brightness [1]. In 1917, Slipher had calculated the radial velocities of 25 "Spiral nebulae", out of which three are moving away, thus underlining the concept of the expansion of the universe [2]. Big – Bang theory with the expansion of the universe [3]. Edwin Hubble and Georges Lemaitre gave birth to the Hubble – Lemaitre law [4]. Calculating the present value of Hubble parameter H_0 by the relation between the radial velocity of galaxies and their distances [5]. Value of H_0 obtained from the planck 2018 of Λ CDM model is 67.04 ± 0.5 km/s/Mpc [6], and according to the SHOES team value is 73.04 ± 1.04 km/s/Mpc [7]. The value of H_0 obtained from the above said teams shows discrepancy known as Hubble tension which still exists. Inhomogeneity concept of the universe with the distribution of galaxies and cosmic structure which are not uniform and also with some differences in the density of matter [8]. Early Dark Energy (EDE) models which was used to study the early expansion of the universe. [9]. Modified gravity as a F(R) gravity [10, 11]. Phantom energy as a dark energy with "W < -1" and Relativistic Degree of Freedom [12]. Vacuum energy as a dark energy which interacts with matter and radiation [13]. Estimating the value of H_0 by using the black holes shadow through observation and Cosmic distance estimation [14]. Estimating the value of H_0 through statistical method by Grey sirens [15]. Ellipsoidal Geometry with anisotropy universe and not a isotropy in the FLRW model [16]. To resolve the Hubble tension by using quantum gravity [17]. Solving the Hubble tension from CMB temperature extraction method with $H_0 = 66.8713$ km/s/Mpc and $H_0 = 66.8945$ km/s/Mpc [23] are the papers regarding resolving the Hubble tension. But Hubble tension still exists and there is no clear or correct solution to this present issue.

In our worksheet we demonstrate that using the respective value of H_0 from Planck 2018 - team and SHOES-team and calculating the CMB temperature (T) for each of these methods not only vary among themselves but also differ largely from the present CMB temperature of 2.725K. In our method we derive a relationship between Hubble's constant H_0 and CMB temperature (T) by first finding the ratio between X-Energy and CMB Energy. We have named this ratio as "Dark Constant" and using this ratio we establish the relationship between X-Energy and CMB (T) as well as the relationship between X-Energy and H_0 . Using all these relationships we derive the correct value for H_0 and its associated CMB (T), which matches the present CMB temperature of 2.725K. The value of Planck's constant (h) used in our calculations is $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ Js [21]. We now proceed to provide the proofs with mathematical equations and examples in the following sections of this paper.

2. Dark Constant(DC):

Since the CMB is a perfect black body radiation and its energy radiation can be calculated by the Planck's famous formula

$$E = h \nu \quad (1)$$

Now the above equation (1) can be written as follows,

$$E_{\text{Cmb}} = h\nu_{\text{cmb}} \quad (2)$$

Where E_{cmb} is the energy of the CMB radiation in joule, h is the Planck's constant and ν is the peak frequency of CMB radiation in Hz or s^{-1}

Now the ratio of the X-Energy with the Energy of the CMB radiation is called as the Dark Constant. This Constant is the dimensionless Constant. This can be expressed in the equation as,

$$\frac{\text{X-Energy}}{\text{CMB-Energy}} = \frac{E_x}{E_{\text{cmb}}} = \text{Dark Constant(DC)} \quad (3)$$

Value of Dark Constant,(DC) is $1.46594448887768 \times 10^{-29}$

In the same way, ratio of the Hubble Constant H_0 with the frequency ν of CMB is called as the Dark Constant (DC) and it can be expressed as follows,

$$\frac{H_0}{\nu_{\text{cmb}}} = \text{Dark Constant(DC)} \quad (4)$$

H_0 is the Hubble constant and it is expressed in s^{-1} and ν_{cmb} is the frequency of CMB radiation in s^{-1} . Like that T_p and T_u can related as

$$\frac{T_p}{T_u} = \text{Dark Constant(DC)} \quad (5)$$

Where T_p is the Time period in s and T_u is the age of the universe in s

3. Relationship between X-Energy & CMB Temperature (T):

We know that,

$$h \nu = 2.8214 \times K \times T \quad (\text{According to the Reference paper [18]}) \quad (6)$$

Above equation can be rearranged as:

$$h \nu_{\text{cmb}} = 2.8214 \times K \times T \quad (7)$$

Since $E = h \nu$ equation (7) can be rearrange as follows,

$$E_{\text{cmb}} = 2.8214 \times K \times T \quad (8)$$

Where E_{cmb} is the energy of CMB radiation in joule, K is Boltzmann constant and T is the CMB temperature in Kelvin (common to both early and late universes), according to the Reference paper [19] value of the Boltzmann constant is $1.380649 \times 10^{-23} \text{J/K}$. Substitute

$E_{\text{cmb}} = E_x / \text{Dark Constant}$ in equation (8):

$$\frac{E_x}{\text{Dark Constant}} = (2.8214) \times (K) \times (T) \quad (9)$$

Rearranging the above equation (9), we get:

$$E_x = (2.8214) \times (K) \times (T) \times (\text{DC}) \quad (10)$$

Substitute $K = 1.380649 \times 10^{-23}$, $\text{DC} = 1.46594448887768 \times 10^{-29}$ in the above equation

(10), we get:

$$E_x = 5.71038605191071 \times 10^{-52} \times T \quad (11)$$

(Or)

$$E_x = \Delta \times T \quad (12)$$

Where E_x is the X- Energy expressed in joule, T is the CMB Temperature in Kelvin and Δ is the Constant and the value is $5.71038605191071 \times 10^{-52} \text{J/K}$.

Highlight points:

(1) X-ENERGY E_x is directly proportional to the CMB Temperature (T)

(2) This formula can be directly used for the late & the early universe.

(3) Increasing of (T) causes the X-Energy (Ex) to increase.

(4) Decreasing of (T) causes the X-Energy (Ex) to decrease

(5) Points (3) & (4) confirms that the Temperature (T) is very high when the age of the universe is 1s ($T=1.16035414939817 \times 10^{18} \text{K}$) see Example 7: and the Temperature (T) is gradually decreases to the present Cosmic Microwave Background Temperature $T=2.725 \text{K}$ (Value of T according to the Reference Paper [20])

4. Estimating X-Energy:

Example: 1 To find out the X-Energy Ex given that CMB temperature is 2.725 K (according to the Reference paper [20])

We know that,

$$\begin{aligned} E_x &= \Delta \times T \text{ from equation} & (12) \\ &= 5.71038605191071 \times 10^{-52} \times 2.725 \\ &= 1.55608019914567 \times 10^{-51} \text{J} \end{aligned}$$

Example 1a:

To find out the X - energy (Ex) given that temperature (T) is $1.16035414939817 \times 10^{18} \text{K}$

[value T is taken from Example 7] and the age of the universe is 1s.

Solution:

$$\begin{aligned} E_x &= \Delta \times T \text{ from equation} & (12) \\ &= (5.71038605191071 \times 10^{-52}) \times (1.16035414939817 \times 10^{18}) = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \end{aligned}$$

5. Showing Relationship between X-Energy (Ex) & H_0 :

We know that,

$$E_{\text{cmb}} = h \times v_{\text{cmb}} \quad \text{from equation} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Substitute } v_{\text{cmb}} = \frac{1}{T_p}$$

We get:

$$E_{\text{cmb}} = \frac{h}{T_p} \quad (13)$$

Substitute $T_p = T_u \times \text{Dark Constant (DC)}$ from equation (5) to the above equation (13), we get:

$$E_{\text{cmb}} = \frac{h}{T_u \times \text{DC}} \quad (14)$$

Substitute Age of the universe $T_u = 1/H_0$ in the above said equation (14), we get:

$$E_{\text{cmb}} = \frac{(h) \times (H_0)}{\text{DC}} \quad (15)$$

Substitute $E_{\text{cmb}} = E_x/\text{DC}$ in the above said equation (15), we get:

$$\frac{E_x}{\text{DC}} = \frac{(h) \times (H_0)}{\text{DC}}$$

Simplifying the above, we get the final equation as,

$$E_x = h \times H_0 \quad (16)$$

Where E_x is the X - Energy and it's expressed in Joule, h is the Planck's constant and H_0 is the Hubble's constant expressed in S^{-1} .

6. Showing Relationship between H_0 & CMB Temperature (T)

Equating equation (12) & (16) equation

$$E_x = \Delta \times T \quad \text{from equation} \quad (12)$$

$$E_x = h \times H_0 \quad \text{from equation} \quad (16)$$

$$h \times H_0 = \Delta \times T$$

Or, $H_0 = \Delta \times T/h$, substituting Δ/h as S' , we get:

$$H_0 = S' \times T \quad (17)$$

Hubble's constant H_0 is directly proportional to the CMB temperature (T) and the above equation (17) clearly shows that the value of H_0 depends on the CMB temperature (T). H_0 is the Hubble's constant expressed in s^{-1} and S' is a constant & its value is:

$$S' = 8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19} \text{K}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{ or Hz/K} \quad (17a)$$

7. Solution to Hubble Tension:

There are papers which tries to give solution to the Hubble tension but still the contention over the Hubble constant value presented by these various researches remains. Equation (17) shows the relationship between H_0 & T (CMB Temperature). Current measurement of the CMB Temperature according to the Reference paper [20] is 2.725K and this Temperature is uniform across the

sky. Presence of the important relationship between these two (H_0 & T) could eliminate the present issue or tension. This can be explained via two conditions as stated below:

(1) Value of H_0 is correct when the value of (T) equals the present value of 2.725 K ($T = 2.725$ K)

(2) Value of H_0 is not correct when the value of (T) unequal the value of 2.725 K ($T \neq 2.725$ K)

Example: 2

Value of H_0 obtained according to the Planck 2018 of Λ CDM model is 67.04 ± 05 Km/s/Mpc. Find the CMB Temperature?

According to the Reference paper [22] Km/s/Mpc is converted to s^{-1}

$$\rightarrow 67.04 / 3.08567758128 \times 10^{19}$$

$$\rightarrow H_0 = 2.17261843579233 \times 10^{-18} s^{-1}$$

We know that, $H_0 = S' \times T$ from equation (17)

$$T = \frac{H_0}{S'} \quad (\text{From the above equation})$$

Substituting the values of H_0 and S' as below

$$T = \frac{2.17261843579233 \times 10^{-18}}{8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19}}$$

Hence, the final resultant value for T is:

$$T = 2.52100681703058K \quad (18)$$

Value of H_0 is not correct since the above result (18) will not equal to the present value of the CMB Temperature whose value is 2.725K. ($2.521K \neq 2.725K$)

Example: 3

Value of H_0 obtained according to the SHOES team are 73.04 ± 1.04 Km/s/Mpc. Goal is to find the CMB temperature.

According to the Reference paper [22] Km/s/Mpc is converted to s^{-1}

$$\rightarrow 73.04 / 3.08567758128 \times 10^{19}$$

$$\rightarrow H_0 = 2.36706519317231 \times 10^{-18} s^{-1} \quad (18a)$$

We know that, $H_0 = S' \times T$ from equation (17), which can be rewritten as below.

$$T = \frac{H_0}{S'}$$

Applying the values for S' and H_0 from equations 17a and 18a we get:

$$T = \frac{2.36706519317231 \times 10^{-18}}{8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19}}$$

$$T = 2.74663391879346 K \quad (19)$$

Value of H_0 is not correct since the above result (19) will not equal to the present value of the CMB temperature whose value is 2.725K. ($2.746K \neq 2.725$)

Example: 4

To find the present value of H_0 when the CMB Temperature is 2.725K

We know that,

$$\rightarrow H_0 = S' \times T \text{ from equation (17)}$$

$$\rightarrow = (8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19}) \times (2.725) \text{ (value 2.725K from Reference paper [20])}$$

$$\rightarrow H_0 = 2.34842095528625 \times 10^{-18} s^{-1}$$

Convert the above value H_0 into Km/s/Mpc

$$\rightarrow H_0 = 72.4646989313493 \text{ Km/s/Mpc}$$

Thus for the present CMB temperature 2.725K correct Hubble's constant H_0 is 72.4646989313493 Km/s/Mpc. This is the solution for the present issue or Hubble tension.

8. Estimating the value of Dark Constant (DC):

Example 5:

To find out the value of Dark Constant given that the X-Energy (E_x) is $= 1.556080199145 67 \times 10^{-51}$ J (taken from Example 1) and the present CMB temperature is 2.725K and with CMB frequency is 160.2GHz. (The given CMB Temperature and Frequency values are according to Reference paper [20])

Solution:

$$\text{Dark Constant, (DC)} = \frac{E_x}{E_{cmb}} \quad \text{from equation} \quad (3)$$

Substitution, $E_{cmb} = h \times V_{cmb}$ from equation (2), wherein $h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ Js (Planck's constant according to the Reference paper [21])

$$V_{\text{cmb}} = \frac{2.8214KT}{h} = \frac{(2.8214 \times 1.380649 \times 10^{-23} \times 2.725)}{6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}} = 160.198491355166 \text{ GHz.}$$

(Or) $V_{\text{cmb}} = 160.2 \text{ GHz}$ approximately.

Substitute $h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ & $V_{\text{cmb}} = 160198491355.166 \text{ Hz}$ in the above said equation (2)

$$E_{\text{cmb}} = (6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}) \times (160198491355.166)$$

$$E_{\text{cmb}} = 1.0614864416435 \times 10^{-22} \text{ J}$$

$$\text{Dark Constant, (DC)} = \frac{1.55608019914567 \times 10^{-51}}{1.0614864416435 \times 10^{-22}} = 1.46594448887768 \times 10^{-29}$$

9. Estimating the total age of the universe:

Example 6

To estimate the total age of the universe

Solution:

X – Energy, $E_x = \Delta \times T$ from equation (12)

Put $T = 1\text{K}$ in the above said equation, we get:

$$E_x = \Delta$$

$$E_x = 5.7103860519107 \times 10^{-52} \text{ J}$$

$H_0 = S' \times T$ from equation (17)

Put $T = 1\text{K}$ in the above said equation

$$H_0 = S'$$

Now Hubble's constant.

$$H_0 = 8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

Convert the above value s^{-1} into Km/s/Mpc

$$H_0 = 26.5925500665502 \text{ Km/s/Mpc}$$

Age of the universe T_u is calculated by the formula

$$T_u = \frac{1}{H_0}$$

Substitute $H_0 = 8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19}$ in the above said equation

Age of the universe,

$$T_u = \frac{1}{(8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19})} = 1.16035414939417 \times 10^{18} \text{ s}$$

(Or)

Converting seconds to Billion Years, total age of the universe is:

$$T_u = 36.77 \text{ Billion Years}$$

10. Estimating the Temperature (T) when the age of the universe is 1 second:

Example: 7

We know that

$$T_u = \frac{1}{H_o}$$

Substitute $T_u = 1s$ in the above equation

We get:

$$H_o = 1s^{-1}$$

$$H_o = S' \times T \text{ from equation}$$

(17)

Rearranging the above equation,

$$T = \frac{H_o}{S'}$$

Substitute $S' = 8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19}$ from equation 17a and $H_o = 1s$ in the above said equation, we get the value of T as below:

$$T = \frac{1}{8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19}} = 1.16035414939817 \times 10^{18} \text{K}$$

Thus when the age of the universe is 1s, the value of Temperature (T) is

$$1.16035414939817 \times 10^{18} \text{K}$$

11. Conclusion:

- 1) Ratio of X-Energy (Ex) with the Energy of CMB radiation (E_{cmb}) is called as the Dark Constant & it's value is $1.46594448887768 \times 10^{-29}$. Throughout the universe it's always be a Constant. [See Example 5:]
- 2) For the present CMB Temperature (2.725 K), the X-Energy (Ex) is $1.55608019914567 \times 10^{-51} \text{J}$. (Example1)
- 3) When the age of the universe is 1s, value of the Temperature (T) is $1.16035414939817 \times 10^{18} \text{K}$ & value of the X-Energy (Ex) is $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{J}$ (Example 7 & 1a)
- 4) Equation (17) shows the relationship between Hubble Constant (H_o) & CMB Temperature T.
- 5) Since the present CMB Temperature is 2.725K and it's uniform across the sky, with the presence of above mentioned relationship could eliminate the present issue (or) Hubble tension.
- 6) By using the two conditions, present issue or Hubble tension could be solved.

Condition 1:

Value of H_o is correct when the value of (T) equals the present value of 2.725K ($T = 2.725 \text{K}$).

Condition 2:

Value of H_o is not correct when the value of (T) not equals to the value of 2.725K ($T \neq 2.725 \text{K}$).

- 7) Value of CMB Temperature T differs from each other for the two respective teams. [Example 2 & 3]

(a) Planck 2018 Λ CDM model is $67.04 \pm 05 \text{ Km/s/Mpc}$ (H_o) with $2.52100681703058 \text{K}$ (T)

(b) SHOES team are $73.04 \pm 1.04 \text{ Km/s/Mpc}$ (H_o) with $2.74663391879346 \text{K}$ (T)

- 8) $H_o = 72.4646989313493 \text{ Km/s/Mpc}$ for the present CMB Temperature 2.725K. [refer Example 4:] and this is the solution for the present issue or Hubble tension.

- 9) Showing the relationship between X- Energy and CMB Temperature (T) with new Constant $\Delta = 5.71038605191071 \times 10^{-52} \text{J/K}$

- 10) Showing the relationship between H_o (Hubble's constant) & CMB Temperature T With new constant $S' = 8.61805855150916 \times 10^{-19} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ or Hz/K .

- 11) Total age of the universe is estimated as $T_u = 36.77 \text{ Billion Years}$ [see Example 6:]

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